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INDIVIDUAL COMPOSITION OF CRYSTALLINE COMPONENTS OF GEORGIAN PETROLEUM

Natela Khetsuriani

TSU, Petre Melikishvili Institute of Physical and Organic Chemistry, 31 Politkovskaia, 0186, Tbilisi, Georgia

Elza Topuria

TSU, Petre Melikishvili Institute of Physical and Organic Chemistry, 31 Politkovskaia, 0186, Tbilisi, Georgia

Irina Mchedlishvili

TSU, Petre Melikishvili Institute of Physical and Organic Chemistry, 31 Politkovskaia, 0186, Tbilisi, Georgia

Madlena Chkhaidze

TSU, Petre Melikishvili Institute of Physical and Organic Chemistry, 31 Politkovskaia, 0186, Tbilisi, Georgia

Georgian petroleum deposits are known since the ancient times. There are more than 1500 manifestations of oil and gas fields. According to quantitative estimates of oil and gas resources (2002) it is determined that geological resource of petroleum in Georgia makes up to 850 million tons, including 400 million tons on the shelf of the Black Sea shelf and remaining 450 million tons on the land. Anticipated resource of gas is estimated up to 180 billion m³ only on land. As a result 1 gas (5.3 trillion cubic meters) and 16 petroleum fields were discovered.

Systematic research of Georgian petroleum began in the 50's of the last century at the Petre Melikishvili Institute of Physical and Organic Chemistry under the guidance of the academician Leonide Melikadze and continues to this very day. It is established that there are all known types of petroleum in Georgia. Because of low content of sulfur and tar-asphaltenic compounds Georgian petroleum is the best raw material for technological processing.

The main goal of the present work was investigation of petroleum from Norio deposit with the high boiling fractions rich in aromatic hydrocarbons and characterized by high intensity luminescence. The sphere of our interest was identification of aromatic compounds in crude oils and their separation by modern research methods. The Norio deposit located to the North-East of Tbilisi and at a distance of 30-35 km from it is associated with sedimentary rocks of the Middle Miocene, the lower and middle Sarmatian layers. Depth of oil and gas horizons makes 1200 m. Relatively deep-seated horizons have not been studied and are considered to be the prospective object for petroleum and gas exploration [1].

Samples of Norio petroleum from wells #200 and #201 were selected for analysis. The physical and chemical and geochemical characteristics as well as the group hydrocarbon composition of Norio petroleum wells with different depths of occurrence were studied. Their physical and chemical characteristics are presented in Table 1. It has been established that this petroleum is characterized by a low content of sulfur, paraffin hydrocarbons and asphaltenes. Petroleum of the Norio deposit belongs to the naphthenoaromatic type. As a study object was selected vacuum distillation fraction 340-590⁰C.

A complex method for aromatic hydrocarbons separation, consisting of atmospheric and vacuum distillation, selective extraction of aromatics by aniline and by liquid-adsorption chromatography on aluminum oxide of the obtained extracts was developed. 1000 concentrates of aromatic hydrocarbon were obtained: petroleum ether eluates and benzene extracts. By their crystallization and recrystallization 90 white and yellow crystalline

compounds were obtained from petroleum for the first time. These compounds had intense luminescence from blue to yellow-green in the visible part of the spectrum. Their crystalline and orderly structures were confirmed by X-ray structural analysis. Structural-group composition of these components was studied by IR-, UV- and mass- spectrometric methods. It was established that the crystalline compounds of Norio petroleum were hybrid aromatic hydrocarbons with complex structure composed of naphthenic and alkylated naphthalenes, phenanthrenes, chrizens, 3,4-benzphenentrenes, benzfluorenes and pyrenes [2].

Table 1. Physical and chemical characteristics of Norio petroleum

Characteristics	W ell #200	W ell #201	Determination method
Perforation depth, m	12 00	8 40	-
Density at 20 ⁰ C, kg/m ³	843,8	816.3	ASTM D 1298
Density at 15 ⁰ C, kg/m ³	847,4	820.0	ASTM D 1298
Specific gravity, ⁰ API	35,4	41.55	GOST R 51069
Kinematic viscosity, 20 ⁰ C, cSt	6,09	1,89	ASTM D 445
Dynamic viscosity, MPa.s	5,14	1,5	ASTM D 445
Pour point, ⁰ C	> -65	> -72	ASTM D 97
Ash content, %	0,009	0,0075	ASTM D 5630
V/Ni ratio	< 1	< 1	ASTM D5708
Acidity, mg KOH/100 cm ³ of fuel	3,9	2,34	ASTM D664
Acid number	1,5	0,97	ASTM D664
Content, %			
Asphaltenes	0,33	0,328	GOST 11858
Tars	2,2	0,95	GOST 11858
Mechanical impurities	0,11	-	ASTM D 473
Water	0,03	0,03	ASTM D4377
Paraffins	0,34	0,28	GOST 11851
Sulfur	0,15	0,18	ASTM D1266
Distillation, %			ASTM D 86
< 200 ⁰ C	34	46	
< 350 ⁰ C	73	76	

The individual composition of the petroleum eluate and crystalline compounds of the high-boiling fractions of Norio petroleum have been studied by chromatographic, mass-spectral, and chromatomass-spectral methods. Gas chromatographic separation was carried out on the capillary column with programmed temperature (Fig. 1). GC-MS experiment was performed in the magnetic field of the device under standard conditions, data analysis was performed using an automated MS deconvolution and identification system (AMDIS). Based on the analysis of electron ionization fragmentation and GC retention indices, polycyclic aromatic structures in the study eluates were identified: mono- and polyalkyl derivatives of indenes, tetralines, dinaphthylbenzenes, naphthalenes, acenaphthylenes, fluorenes, phenanthrenes, anthracenes, naphthofluorenes and phenanthrenes, as well as terphenyls.

Figure 1. GC of a petroleum ether eluate concentrate

In crystalline components separated from the eluate the following compounds were identified: benzanthracenes, chrysenes, their methyl-, dimethyl- and trimethyl-analogues, phenanthrene derivatives, anthracenes and pyrenes (figure 2). Mass-spectra of phenanthrene and its derivatives identified in crystalline components are presented on figure 3 [3, 4].

Figure. 2. GC of crystallization (a) and recrystallization (b) products obtained from petroleum ether eluate. Major components: I, I' - benz[a]anthracene and chrysene, their II - methyl-, III - dimethyl- and IV - trimethyl-derivatives, V – substituted phenanthrenes, anthracenes, pyrenes

Figure 3. Mass spectra of (a) 4-methyl-, 3,6-dimethyl-, 2,3,5-trimethyl- and 3,4,5,6-tetramethylphenanthrenes

On the basis of the TIC (Total Ionic Chromatogram) of the crystalline samples for the first time in Georgian crude oils were identified the sulfur and nitrogen heteroanalogues of high-molecular polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: benzonaphthothiophenes in the “benzanthracene” fraction, benzocarbazole and dibenzthiophenes in the “phenanthrene” fraction [5].

It was found that isolated crystalline substances are native components of petroleum and not the products formed during its processing. It was on the basis of the fluorescent components of Norio petroleum that the technological process for production of luminophore “Noriol” was further developed and has found wide practical application for luminescent defectoscopy of critical machine parts and metal constructions.

Conclusion

A method for the preliminary extraction of aromatic hydrocarbons from crude oils was shown to be sufficient for the successful determination of 280 of these hydrocarbons at a molecular level by traditional GC-MS.

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OFFSHORE POWER PLANT

Assylkanym Kassayeva

Associated professor of Caspian State university of technologies and engineering named after S. Yessenov, 130003, 32 Md., Aktau, Republic of Kazakhstan

Abstract. The amount of ocean wave energy available worldwide is large enough to generate serious interest in its extraction and use, and to make a significant contribution to meeting the energy aspirations of various consumers. The amount of marine energy is fundamentally greater than the amount of energy on land, yet the introduction of wave energy conversion systems in offshore power plants remains a costly initiative. The relevance of the published study is justified by the fact that ocean waves provide an inexpensive and environmentally friendly energy resource suitable for simple wave energy generation through offshore power plants. The purpose of this study is to analyse the technological characteristics, depending on the localisation resource potential of wave energy generating offshore power plants, focusing on the hydrodynamic characteristics of offshore power plants during the analysis. The subject of the study is modern technologies for harnessing ocean wave energy in an offshore power plant format, with realistic prospects for reaching the commercial stage of power generation, along with wind and solar power. PyFerret software was used to analyse the data. The Ferret software was upgraded to the PyFerret version based on the Python application. The PyFerret software is a carrier of complex and multiple data for analysis. It is designed and produced specifically for meteorologists and oceanographers, and runs on UNIX and Mac operating systems. The PyFerret software applies data on wind and atmospheric pressure obtained from the ECMWF database, in formats such as Netcdf, ASCII and binary code. The originality of the published study is related to the technological trend to improve the efficiency and competitiveness of the wave energy generating offshore power plants, to reduce the cost and congestion of deployed offshore power plant systems, especially in remote areas.

Keywords: Energy storage system; technological advances; wave energy conversion; optimum solution; efficient operation; achieving resonance.

Introduction

One of the most important imperatives in today's global paradigm is the demand for renewable energy supply, as renewable energy has no negative impact on the environment. The use of new and renewable sources of energy derived from natural resources [1] is needed in particular to provide electricity to remote areas of the planet. The relevance of the published study is justified by the fact that ocean waves are now universally recognised as a productive and sustainable source of energy. They provide humans with an inexpensive and environmentally friendly energy resource, suitable for simple wave power generation through offshore power plants. The amount of ocean wave energy available worldwide is large enough [2] to generate serious interest in its extraction and use, and to make a significant contribution to meeting the energy aspirations of various consumers.

However, despite numerous attempts, the commercial exploitation of offshore power plants has progressed extremely slowly [3], compared to the commercial exploitation of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar. It is indeed problematic to design a high-efficiency offshore power plant [4], as the wave power generation converter system is usually a pendulum system submerged in the oscillating water column. Wave energy is generated by converting the inertia of a sea wave into mechanical energy, which is then converted into electrical energy. This forces developers to address technological problems [5], ranging from

the variability of ocean wave properties to the survivability of offshore power plants in harsh ocean conditions. The rapid progress of the wave energy industry has been hampered by the lack of standard procedures and criteria associated with the selection of a suitable technology [6], as there are difficulties arising from the need to quantify wave energy. Unlike wind turbines, where an increase in wind speed or blade area results in an increase in the energy produced, the interaction of offshore power plants with ocean waves causes differences in their energy absorption characteristics.

The purpose of this study is to analyse the technological characteristics, depending on the localisation resource potential of wave energy generating offshore power plants, focusing on the hydrodynamic characteristics of offshore power plants during the analysis. The subject of the study is modern technologies for harnessing ocean wave energy in an offshore power plant format, with realistic prospects for reaching the commercial stage of power generation, along with wind and solar power.

A key factor in assessing the performance of wave energy converters using offshore power plants [7], appears to be consumer interest in the cost of the generated energy. Potential investors in the wave energy sector will only be interested before they start designing and deploying offshore power plants if the investment yields a reasonable return. Offshore energy plants must therefore not only be profitable but also competitive [8], as ocean waves are not among the only renewable energy resources on the planet. Thus, in addition to increasing power generation using offshore power plants, compared to current production rates, there is a need [9] to simultaneously reduce the cost of power generation, and increase the reliability of the entire system. Given the fact that it is more expensive to develop renewable energy sources than to develop conventional energy sources, there has previously been little interest in developing renewable energy sources.

The originality of the published study is related to the technological trend, according to which, in the modern world, the perspective on the development of renewable energy sources has changed dramatically. For decades, the development of clean, low-cost, long-term forms of energy, such as hydropower, solar, wind, geothermal, wave and tidal energy, has undergone rapid technological growth. Extensive further research and technological developments are required to improve the efficiency and competitiveness of offshore wave power plants, to reduce the cost and congestion of implemented offshore power plant systems, especially in remote areas.

Materials and Methods

The research issue of hydrodynamic modelling of wave energy fleets using analytical methods, which forms the basis of this study, has its origins in the seminal works on wave energy. By applying the acoustic theory of diffraction on multiple bodies to waves on water, it was possible to create a multiple scattering method for the study of offshore platforms, which was later applied to the field of wave energy. In the iterative multiple scattering method, the properties of diffraction and radiation of isolated bodies are used, and the reflected waves within the array are added iteratively until convergence is achieved. The iterative multiple scattering method has been combined with the direct matrix method. The resulting multiple scattering method [10], enables the wave amplitude around each body to be calculated simultaneously, without iteration, and is accurate with respect to linear potential flow theory. Subsequently, the multiple scattering method has been combined with a numerical method allowing the use of arbitrary geometry, and has been applied to the study of the interaction of wave energy parks with captured wave conditions [11]. The wave energy park has been investigated using analytical methods such as matched asymptotic and multipole decompositions.

Hydrodynamic modelling in marine engineering is most often carried out using numerical methods. The most commonly used approach is the boundary element method using BEM software. The boundary element method [12] discretises the boundaries of the fluid region, and proceeds from an integral representation of the fluid velocity potential. In the context of wave propagation models, such as MILDwave or OceanWave3D, a perturbed wave over a large area of the ocean with different depths is studied. The hydrodynamic interactions are then modelled based on wave energy parks.

Several neural network architectures were applied to predict the non-linear dynamic process of water level fluctuations. Artificial neural network structures are leading to the mass adoption of new computing technologies that resemble human approaches to information processing. Neural networks are organised hierarchically, by neuron layer, to process non-linear signals. Information is collected at the input level, and then passed on to the network through processing at hidden levels. This procedure continues until the output layer, which presents the results of the network.

PyFerret software was used to analyse the data. The Ferret software has been upgraded to PyFerret [13], based on a Python application. The PyFerret software is a carrier of complex and multiple data for analysis. It is designed and produced specifically for meteorologists and oceanographers, and runs on UNIX and Mac operating systems. The PyFerret software applies data on wind and atmospheric pressure from the ECMWF database, in formats such as Netcdf, ASCII and binary code.

Results

The offshore power plant is an energy wave generator that converts vertical wave power into motion energy. It provides the rotation of a water turbine connected to an electric generator by placing a pump piston directly connected to the pontoon and cylinder. The pump is installed on the seabed. With the rapid technological advances in the field of offshore power plants, the application of target function algorithms in various branches of wave engineering, has led to a significant increase in the variety of engineering problems. In practice, there is a widening possibility to observe the results of applying the target function algorithms [14] in various branches of wave engineering. Thus, a simulator or a mathematical function, referred to as a target function, serves to make a comparison between them, and to select the optimum configuration, depending on the wave energy. Each target function algorithm in the various branches of wave engineering has several independent variables known as design variables. The purpose of the target function algorithms in the various wave engineering branches, is to determine the optimal design variables to minimise or maximise the target function.

In recent years, the application of evolutionary algorithms to problems related to sea wave energy conversions by offshore power plants has been developed. Due to sufficiently fast and efficient evolutionary algorithms and swarm intelligence techniques, significant advances have been made. One of the most important breakthroughs is the setting of power take-off parameters for each wave energy converter, which depends on location, geometric parameters and sea conditions. The application of hybrid power take-off parameters, such as spring stiffness and damping factor, incorporating local search, evolutionary algorithms, and surrogate methods, has expanded in recent years by improving alternative approaches to traditional offshore power plant strategies. In particular, the genetic algorithm and the firefly swarm optimisation algorithm have proven to be in demand for testing a method of locating the structural components of the offshore power plant converters.

The applied algorithms for maximising the total power output of offshore power plants are divided into two categories, the heuristic and the metaheuristic. Heuristic algorithms are

captured at local optimal points and converge to these points. Metaheuristic algorithms are in fact based on local optimal points [15], and along with the simplicity and flexibility of the solution, they allow for their application in a wide range of wave energy issues in the field of offshore power plants. The number of solutions evaluated in each algorithm iteration cycle serves as a criterion for classifying the target functions in the various branches of wave engineering. Accordingly, target function algorithms, in the various branches of wave engineering, fall into two categories of solution-based methods. These are the metaheuristic algorithm and the optimisation algorithm.

An attempt to use an offshore power plant algorithm, called the optimiser, in calculating and comparing point depths, to the wave power at each point, as a predictable trend of change, has shown that wave power tends to be higher at deeper points. In other words, the onshore points are characterised by lower wave power. Notably, although the amount of marine energy is fundamentally greater than the amount of energy on land, it is still a costly initiative to introduce wave energy conversion systems at offshore power plants. Moreover, changes in wave energy level are more dependent on wave height than on wave depth. In the case of offshore power plants, the expressed idea can be justified by the non-linear dependence of wave power on wave height.

Electric generators enable offshore power plants to produce mechanical energy from interaction with the ocean or sea waves. The mechanical energy received by offshore power plants from ocean waves is first converted into mechanical rotational or linear reciprocating motion. The rotational motion usually drives a turbine, which rotates an electric generator. On the other hand, translational motion drives a linear electric generator.

Over the last three decades, offshore power plants have become very significant in the field of power generation. Various types of wave power devices have emerged, such as point absorber, shut-off device, oscillating water column, ripple wave converter, immersion pressure converter, convex wave converter. Point absorber is one of the most cost-effective varieties of offshore power plants. It is equipped with moving parts, the horizontal size of which is smaller than the vertical one, enabling the benefits of the wave impact to be concentrated at one point. One part of the point absorber is almost stationary and the other part is located near the sea surface. The point absorber moves perpendicularly, capturing wave energy which drives a linear generator to produce electricity. There are various point absorbers, particularly the well-known Power Buoy, produced by the American state-owned renewable energy company, Ocean Power Technologies.

An example of an offshore power plant with surplus wave power is Wave Dragon, which functions using the wave energy absorption method. When a wave passes through a turbine, which is connected to a rotating electrical generator, the turbine produces electrical energy from both potential energy and kinetic energy. This is because the potential energy is continuously, after a few moments, converted into kinetic energy.

Offshore power plants of the oscillating water column type, embedded in rocks, and located close to the seabed. They generate electricity by using abundant ocean or sea wave energy. When a wave enters the chambers of an offshore power plant of the oscillating water column type, the water level inside the chamber rises, creating high air pressure which drives the turbine. The air pressure inside the chamber under this condition is much higher than the atmospheric pressure. When the water returns to the sea, the air pressure inside the chamber becomes much lower than the atmospheric pressure. For this reason, air flows again into the oscillating water column type offshore power plant chamber from outside, driving the turbine so as to produce electricity. An example of an offshore power plant of the oscillating water column type is the Wavegen Limpet.

This is a schematic diagram of an alternative power plant that converts wave energy into electricity. It is essentially an offshore hydroelectric power plant, which in many ways is similar to a conventional hydroelectric power plant. An interesting fact is that the construction cost, per megawatt of electricity, is ten times cheaper in these plants than in nuclear ones, with a wave of only 0.3m. With higher waves, it would be even lower. And with a wave of 2m, that cost would only be \$100.000. It is known that the capacity of any hydroelectric power plant is determined by two parameters. These are the water head, measured in metres of water column, where 10m of water column equals one atmosphere, and the water discharge, measured in m³/sec. This design fully supplies the hydraulic units with the specified amount of water and the required head. But unlike conventional hydroelectric power stations, where the flow rate is a finite value, for each, specific river, it has the undeniable advantage - for offshore hydroelectric power plants, the water discharge can be any required value, determined by the number of operating cylinders. And this is an undeniable advantage over conventional hydroelectric plants, given that the construction cost per each megawatt generated is much lower than that of conventional hydroelectric plants. And besides, the head can be adjusted in tens or hundreds of metres of water column. There are only a handful of such adequate high-rise dams in the world. And considering that, combined with this head, the water consumption can be anything, the power output can be anything as well. Moreover, given that the construction cost per megawatt of an offshore hydroelectric plant is much lower than that of conventional energy sources, hydroelectric plants of the offshore type will certainly dominate the world's energy supply in the future. If the site for such a plant is chosen so that the shoreline is the boundary between the sea and a high, mountainous shore, it is advisable to design it together with a pumped-storage plant. Part of the cylinders will directly pump water into the reservoir located in the mountains. Also, the surplus water after the compensation columns will not be discharged into the sea but will also be pumped into the reservoir. As the wave amplitude decreases, the power will be compensated by the operation of the pumped-storage plant.

There is almost no environmental damage caused by this plant. There are grids on the intake openings of the pontoon pumps to prevent sea creatures from entering the technological grid. Moreover, if necessary, the entire unit can be fenced off with fine mesh around the perimeter. Technogenic accidents with catastrophic consequences, such as those at hydroelectric power stations when dams collapse, are completely ruled out. And even if one were to imagine the possibility of a marine hydropower station being destroyed by a tsunami, sabotage, military action, there would be virtually no environmental damage.

There is no need to master any new technology when using this method of generating clean energy. Everything gathered in this method is already in use in various industries, along with repair, installation and service techniques. The power that can be generated is so enormous that it could well surpass conventional energy sources. The cost of electricity generated, on the other hand, may well be lower than that of conventional power.

The design of the offshore power plant is on the principle of a surface attenuator, almost exactly in line with the direction of the waves [17]. An offshore power plant based on the surface attenuator principle is constructed of interconnected sections, including main tubes and bends, which move when a wave hits the segments of the unit in succession. The main tube of the offshore power plant, on the principle of a surface attenuator, comprises a bow tube, a centre tube and an end tube. Inside the tubes, the power conversion module is placed between the two main tubes. The Pelamis offshore power units, manufactured by the PelamisWave Power company according to the surface attenuator principle, are most commonly used in the power industry.

Discussion

Offshore power plants are not being developed solely for the purpose of converting ocean wave energy into electrical power. The areas of implementation of offshore power plants include offshore oil and gas extraction, desalination, island power microgrids, artificial reefs, protection of coastal areas, and aquaculture. One of the world's largest oil and gas companies, Italian ENI Group, has used small offshore power plants on its offshore platforms as charging points and communication devices for the first time. ENI Group, in collaboration with the Polytechnic University of Turin, is working on an industrial model of a rocking device equipped with two gyroscopic systems connected to a generator, with a rated output power of 100 kW at peak [18]. Scottish company Mocean Energy is developing an articulated raft designed to generate electricity from wave energy, power subsea control systems, and autonomous remotely operated submersibles in the oil and gas industry.

In the last decade, in the context of wave energy extraction, the use of piezoelectric materials has been widely considered in the design of offshore power plants. The advocates of technological applications [19] of piezoelectric materials J. Briscoe, S. Dunn, A. Erturk, D. J. Inman, etc. seek to convince the scientific community that piezoelectric ceramics are capable of exploiting stress and strain cycles induced by ocean waves to generate output voltage. Piezoelectric materials enable the power take-off mechanism to be incorporated directly into the primary motor, usually in a flexible piezoelectric membrane. This reduces the number of mechanical connections present in the device.

A polemical debate involving scientists and manufacturers M. C. Simoes, S. M. Deckmann, A. H. Bayo, etc. [20], has brought urgent research attention to the heuristically profound issue. It concerns the grid integration of electricity generated by offshore power plants, which produce rapidly fluctuating voltages, known as flicker. Different voltage levels determine different degrees of flicker. Assessing the flicker, or electrical power quality, is therefore a crucial aspect to be considered in the design of offshore power plants. Power peaks decrease as the number of devices increases. The level of flicker is estimated as a function of the grid resistance angle. It is advisable to use specialised power electronics and filtration equipment to reduce flicker and obtain acceptably smooth power generation.

Under current market conditions, the technological status of offshore power plants has influenced the consolidation of the supply and value chain in the ocean wave energy extraction sector. Supply chain consolidation is based on commercially viable technology projects. Compared to the wind energy sector, the demand for original equipment is driven by a strong project pipeline. In the ocean energy field, on the other hand, supply chain consolidation depends on reliability and on advances in technology which are not ready for the market today. The development of wave energy is hampered by a lack of investor confidence in the current technological concepts. One of the most important problems in the ocean energy sector has proven to be the lack of equipment manufacturers. Investors demand evidence that a standardised approach to technology development has been implemented. In the wave energy sector, there are no technologies in the growth phase, as all of them are in their infancy.

One of the most promising development areas for offshore power plants is the use of wave energy to desalinate water. This is especially the case in the regions of the world where there is a shortage of potable water and a significant wave resource is available. Australian company Carnegie Clean Energy has developed the Desalination Pilot Plant on Garden Island, based at the Royal Australian Navy's fleet, as the first commercial desalination project using wave energy. This plant operates with electrical power generated by an offshore power plant. The production capacity of the Desalination Pilot Plant on Garden Island, powered by wave energy from offshore power plants, is around one and a half hundred cubic metres of

potable water per day. Alternative desalination projects based on offshore power plants are represented by the Odysée desalination pump designed in Canada, similar to the Saros desalination unit manufactured in the USA.

Wave energy conversion using offshore power plants appears as a viable alternative to hydrocarbon fuels on remote islands, for which fuel imports can be an unaffordable financial burden. In this context, in Australia, the Desalination Pilot Plant on Garden Island has been supplemented by three 1MW wave buoys, a 2MW solar photovoltaic array, and a 2MW battery powering the largest naval base in Australia. The second project is being realised on King Island by the Wave Swell company, which has deployed a 200kW UniWave200 offshore power plant, intending to connect to the Hydro Tasmania hybrid grid.

The British company CCell is developing a wave paddle with a curved valve to grow coral reefs. The paddle marine power plant system runs a low-voltage electric current through a steel construction that attracts minerals from the seawater. Attracted minerals from seawater form a limestone rock around the steel structure, onto which coral colonies attach themselves. Other applications for offshore power plants in the aquaculture sector include Smalle Technologies eForcis and Albatern's WaveNET, which convert energy from ocean waves into electricity, thus enabling the operation of fish farms.

In the flexible offshore power plants, deformable prime movers are used to drive the power take-off system, instead of the traditional rigid ones. The advantage of deformable prime movers is a reduction in the number of moving metal parts, which often cause serious failures during running tests. The first flexible device concepts, the Lancaster Flexible Bag and Circular Clam, were a series of air-filled inflatable bags. They expanded and contracted following the oscillating movements of the ocean waves, pumping air into a turbine connected to a generator. Admittedly, the judgement of M. G. Say, R. Brooke, J. Edberg, A. Grimoldi, D. Belaineh, I. Engquist [21] that the modern development of flexible devices has been accelerated by the advent of high performance elastic materials such as dielectric elastomers, flexible piezoelectric bimorphs, and flexible fabrics is true.

Various types of flexible devices, in particular deformable membranes, convex wave and carpet membranes, have been extensively tested. Scottish company AWS Ocean Energy is developing several flexible devices on Loch Ness Lake on deformable membranes that use the same operating principle as the air-filled Lancaster Flexible Bag and Circular Clam inflatable bags mentioned above. The unit is made of many inflatable cells arranged around the catamaran structure, in the shape of a regular dodecagon. AWS Ocean Energy is ready to move to the full prototype stage.

The Australian company Bombora has developed the wWave flexible offshore power plant. The wWave plant is equipped with multiple air-inflated rubber membranes mounted on the structure, at a depth of a few metres near the shore. When the waves pass, each membrane pumps air into the channel, driving a turbine connected to a generator.

The convex wave device is an elastic rubber tube filled with water and aligned perpendicular to the wave crests. The waves create a pressure differential that causes a bulge along the length of the tube. Matching the resonance frequency of the convexity with the frequency of the waves maximises energy production. This phenomenon results from the interaction of waves, an elastic tube and internal fluid, and is similar to the pumping of blood in arteries. English company Checkmate Seaenergy has developed the Anaconda convex wave device, in which an elastic tube ends in a turbine connected to a generator.

A direct consequence of using visco-elastic materials, in an authoritative research debate involving R. Alessi, M. Ambati, T. Gerasimov, S. Vidoli, L. De Lorenzis [22], the results of which are widely accepted by the academic and research community, are nowadays accepted as undesirable phenomena such as hysteresis, stress softening and strain-induced

crystallisation. These are fraught with performance problems for convex wave devices subjected to significant deformations. This refers to considerable membranes that are loose in the terminal points and fixed by means of cables or hydraulic pistons.

The basic mode of operating wave-activated offshore power plant oscillating systems involves the generation of oscillating motion during interaction with ocean or sea waves. The oscillating movement is converted into other forms of useful energy, by means of an appropriate power take-off mechanism. Most oscillating offshore power plant systems float on the surface of the ocean. In polemical terms, the advocates of the prospect of industrial operation of offshore power plant oscillation systems among the scientists responsible for development and industrial specialists R. McKee, B. Elsässer, P. Schmitt [23], are attracted precisely by the possibility of significantly improving the efficiency of power generation, given the resonance with the incoming wave. Over the years, various methods have been developed to improve the overall efficiency of oscillating offshore power plant systems, mainly focusing on getting the energy-absorbing part of the plant to function throughout the full resonance period. The fundamental difficulty in this regard lies in the fact that, in reality, the environment of ocean waves is of a random nature. Consequently, the tuning of offshore power plant oscillation systems to resonate with the different frequencies of ocean waves is challenging. Active and passive methods of power take-off tuning are the most common, along with optimising the geometry of offshore power plants. Other methods include reducing the viscous damping that occurs during the movement of the buoy within the water.

Active methods of power take-off tuning differ from passive methods in the respect that active methods are tuned to take power externally from the power generated by the offshore power plant. This is to control the primary wave energy absorber whereas locking and unlocking are examples of passive methods of power take-off tuning and are very common in the studies on offshore power plant optimisation. Locking control is achieved by holding the offshore power plant in a fixed position when the speed is zero, and by releasing the offshore power plant at the right time, so that the speed of the unit is in phase with the driving force, ensuring that resonance is achieved. On the other hand, disconnecting works by decoupling, which means alternatively switching the power take-off system on and off.

As the number and size of offshore power plants increase, the software costs for each configuration grow. This is because an increase in the number of optimisation parameters requires intensification of the time necessary for the convergence of the optimisation algorithms. At the same time, the search space is characterised by a lack of salience and multimodality. Optimisation time could be reduced if hydrodynamic interactions were evaluated analytically, instead of software in the block-element-modifier (BEM) format.

To summarise the study of offshore power plants, it is important to note the significance of the scientific debate on the issues of converting ocean wave energy into electrical energy. A comprehensive study of the issue has highlighted a critical aspect of offshore power plant design, such as the assessment of flicker, or the quality of the generated electricity. A fundamental scientific debate involving experts and academics has led to the reasonable conclusion. In the context of the most promising offshore power plants, such as marine oil and gas extraction, building island power micro-grids, artificial reefs, protection of coastal areas and aquaculture cultivation, there is no alternative to using wave energy to desalinate water, especially in areas of the world where potable water is in short supply.

Conclusions

This study aimed at analysing and presenting the technological characteristics, depending on the localisation resource potential of offshore wave power plants, giving priority to the hydrodynamic characteristics of the offshore power plants during the analysis.

It has been scientifically established that, despite the fact that the amount of marine energy is fundamentally greater than the amount of energy on land, the introduction of wave energy conversion systems in offshore power plants is still a costly undertaking. It has been found that as the number and size of offshore power plants increase, the system costs for each configuration grow. This is because an increase in the number of optimisation parameters requires intensification of the time necessary for the convergence of the optimisation algorithms. At the same time, the search space is characterised by a lack of salience and multimodality. There is a clear need for increased offshore power generation compared to current production rates, with a simultaneous need to reduce the cost of power production, and to increase the reliability of the overall system. Incorporating an energy storage system puts a way into the hands of energy managers to make it easier to manage a low-energy situation.

A limitation of the presented study is the fundamental interdependence of many interrelated factors. In particular, in addition to energy generation as the primary objective of offshore power plant studies, researchers must pay attention to the performance of offshore power plant equipment that has to withstand the harsh conditions of the marine environment. Another limitation of the presented study is caused by the low energy efficiency of offshore power plants. To obtain significant power output, power plants (especially heat exchangers) must be huge in size, hence the immediate investment is high. The sustainable development of offshore power plants urgently requires the latest technological advances in the field of wave energy conversion technology.

The horizons of the presented study can be broadened by introducing more potential variables, e.g., machine stator resistance, irregularity of waves and speed factor. In further studies on offshore power plants, it is appropriate to investigate the variability over time of energy absorption efficiency. Furthermore, it would be useful to investigate methods by which a comprehensive understanding of power could be gained and the commercial and environmental opportunities analysed. Tracking the offshore power plant capacity will enable the monitoring of the growth dynamics of the ocean wave energy industry.

The difference between this method and conventional hydropower lies in the fact that there is no need to build dams, store water, flood areas, and thereby alter and disturb the ecosystem of the land. The platform on which the offshore hydroelectric power station is located occupies a very small area. Water is drawn in unlimited quantities from the aquatic environment, pumped into the hydroelectric turbines and discharged back into the sea. The ecological impact on the environment is minimal. The area required for this process is minimal. The consequences of possible accidents are minor and completely incomparable with possible accidents in hydroelectric power plants, while the power generated is enormous. This energy, as a kind of derivative of solar energy, is eternal. As long as the sun shines, atmospheric processes will take place, the winds will blow and accelerate the sea waves. This is why harnessing this energy is so intriguing. The capacity of a conventional hydroelectric power plant depends directly on the water catchment and head and is therefore limited. By contrast, an offshore power plant can be built at virtually any capacity, as the sea is unlimited. The capacity of an offshore hydroelectric power plant depends only on its scale.

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COMPLEX ESTIMATION OF RADIATION FACTORS FOR PROVIDING OF RADIATION SAFETY OF POPULATION OF WESTERN KAZAKHSTAN AREA

Berdesheva Gulshara Aytkaliyevna

leader of department the "General hygiene", candidate of medical sciences

Abstract: In the article an analysis is conducted and the complex estimation of radiation situation is carried out in western Kazakhstan area, with determination of negative technogenic and radioactive elements in the objects of environment and bio components of man with the further ranging of the studied territory.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, irradiations of population, radiation factors.

Intensive development of oil and gas industry on territory of the western Kazakhstan area for the last decades caused the increase of natural of radiation nucleotides on a terrene. The special attention is deserved by the sources of potential irradiation, such as underground peaceful nuclear explosions and sources, form in mining holes in the process of geophysical researches [1].

Presently the questions of the ecological setting of norms of the anthropogenic changed environment are developed in various directions and with different aims: guard of gene pool of planet; maintenance of the acceptable to the man sanitary state of environment; guard of landscape variety of nature; guard of sources of biological products; guard of recreational resources; maintenance of biological variety and steady development of biosphere. Not all these questions it is possible and needed to decide simultaneously on the same territory. In transition from sanitary-hygienic there is changing of object of setting of norms to ecological principles of setting of norms. Separate not individuals, as a man within the framework of sanitary-hygienic approach, but natural or created by a man systems - populations, ecosystems, come forward in his role [2, 3].

The modern system of setting of norms of radiation factor constantly develops and, at the same time, still remains imperfect. It is expressed and in imperfection of the applied criteria of determination of doses and powers of doses, and in the insufficient account of important parameters and directions of influence of technogenic radiation nuclides on living organisms and their systems, and also effect of influence of technogenic radiation with other sources of contamination [4]. Radiation safety is called to decide two functional tasks: a 1) decline of level of irradiation of personnel and population to regulation on the basis of complex of project, technical, medical and hygienically events; 2) creation of the effective radiation checking system, allowing operatively to register the change of radiation situation, judge the irradiations of personnel and population about levels, radiocontammant of different objects and environment and to take measure on normalization of radiation situation. Research of structure of doses of irradiation of population allows not only to define total effective doses but also serves as basis for planning and realization of optimal events on the decline of doses of irradiation of population. Knowledge of structure of doses allows to plan a decline effective foremost those her constituents that bring in a most contribution to the total doses, at minimum expenses on realization of protective events.

Thus actuality of the real work is determined by null data about the parameters of radiation situation on territory of western Kazakhstan area. It, in turn, hampers an estimation ecologically meaningful radiation factors and development of the most perspective directions of providing of radiation safety of population of region.

Research aim - to carry out the complex estimation of radiation situation in western Kazakhstan area, with determination of negative technogenic and radioactive elements in the

objects of environment and bio components of man with the further ranging of the studied territory.

Under radiation control a complex is understood associate and obligatory for execution of the administrative, organizationally-technical, sanitary-hygienic events and legal measures, sent to the decline of influence of radiation on a population and other categories of the exposed to rays persons [2].

The task of radiation control is a receipt of objective data on a radiation situation. The measureable parameters of objects of radiation control are basic descriptions of factors of radiation-damage on a man, namely: for an external radiation is power of display dose and fluency of particles, for internal is a concentration of radiation nucleotides in the objects of control (water, air, soil, foodstuffs, organism of man of and other). The list of radiation nucleotides subject to setting of norms and control is set by the normative acts of Republic of Kazakhstan.

As is generally known, on territory of western Kazakhstan area the radon measuring of the inhabited places of average annual by volume activity of radon and daughter's products is conducted, and also as evaluated by safety of workplaces of personnel, working as an open source radiation. Radon of map of territory of city for period 2017 year 25 objects of dwellings and public building are inspected, a 48 measuring of by volume activity of radon, thorium (^{228}Ac), radium (^{226}Ra), caesium (^{137}Cs) is conducted. It is not discovered in the investigational tests of exceeding of possible levels.

The basic sources of ionizing radiation, forming a radiation situation on territory of western Kazakhstan area and their contribution is certain to the general structure of external and internal irradiation of population of region, are studied. The most perspective directions of providing of radiation safety of population and control of radiocontammant of environment are reasonable.

The results of estimation of doses are driven to the table.1-3. So, the estimation of doses of external irradiation of habitants came true by means of measuring of power of equivalent dose on the stretch of open country, and also in communal and productive spheres by the attested measuring devices of power of dose of gamma-radiation by the dosimeter of ДКГ-07Д "Thrush" # 7884, certificate of verification # of BA.17-04-28895 from 28.08.2017 . to 28.08.2018., with deduction of the Pre-set own background of device.

In the generalized kind results of the instantaneous and kvazyintegral measuring of ЭРОА of radon and thoron in mid air dwellings, curative prophylactic establishments of settlements is driven to the table.1. As follows from the analysis of these data, value ЭРОА isotopes of radon in mid air apartments of dwellings, public and administrative building hesitate in limits from units *of Bk/m³ to Bk/m³ at a mean value on all results of measuring near Bk/m³.

Table 1

Instrumental measuring of power of effective dose of gamma-radiation

№	object	Place realization of measuring	amount of measuring	Actual value gamma-radiations, mk3v/h	Legitimate values of gamma-radiations, mk3v/h
1	Uralsk city	boulevard is Drujba, №203	2	min -0,06* max- 0,11	State Supervision №155 Division 4 point 30 no more than 0,2
2	Uralsk city	Moldagulova st., №26,	2	min-0,08* max-0,12	
3	Uralsk city	Syrym Datov st., №3	3	min-0,07* max-0,10	
4	Uralsk city	Syrym Datov st., №6	3	min-0,04* max-0,11	
* Measuring was conducted taking into account a radiation background					

The estimation of doses of internal irradiation due to radio-activity in a drinking-water was estimated by means of radio-chemistry methods, and specific activity is in water, determined on new methodology (table. 2).

Table 2

Measuring specific total alpha- ($A\alpha$) and to β activity ($A\beta$) of water

№	address	object	Actual values total α and β activity Bk/kg	
			α activity	β activity
1	boulevard is Drujba, №203	water	0,0372±0,0221	0,1801±0,0786
2	Moldagulova st., №26,	water	0,0295±0,0198	0,2226±0,0837
3	Syrym Datov st., №6	water	0,0271±0,0172	0,1894±0,0806,

Practically in all cases of dose of irradiation of habitants could not be measured directly, therefore the levels of irradiation of habitants were estimated on the derivative indexes of radiation situation, and for a transition from these indexes to the doses of irradiation the calculation methods of dosimetria were used.

Table 3

Measuring of specific activity of natural of radiation nucleotides

№	address	object	Actual values of specific activity, kBk/kg
1	boulevard is Drujba, №203	vegetation,	Cs137-1.98±8,71 Sr90-0
2	Moldagulova st., №26,	vegetation,	Cs137-1,43±2,87 Sr90-0
3	Syrym Datov st., №6	vegetation,	Cs137-1,74±3,75 Sr90-0
4	boulevard is Drujba, №203	soil	K40-367,84±102,6 Th232-10,76±6,34 Ra226-20,44±8,57 Cs137-2,56±0,65
5	Moldagulova st., №26,	soil	K40- 252,2±67,7 Th232-7,36±5,3 Ra226-17,41±4,95 Cs137—3,34±2,41
6	Syrym Datov st., №6	soil	K40-278,3±71,2 Th232-3,77±4,07 Ra226-9,66±4,27 Cs137-4,36±2,49

As a result of undertaken studies complex research of levels of contamination of territory of western Kazakhstan area (Uralsk city) is carried out and the structure of doses of irradiation of habitants of regional center is certain due to the sources of current and potential irradiation and the basic sources of potential irradiation are certain on territory of western Kazakhstan area - object appearing because of underground nuclear explosions in the process of geophysical researches.

It is thus possible to mark that to date a radiation situation on territory of area is characterized as stable, a gamut-background in the districts of area made a mkp/hour. 14 enterprises of area in the work use 73 sources with an ionizing radiation with total activity 268592 Gbk.

Ownerless sources, ionizing radiations and radiocontammants it is not discovered on an area, uranium deposits are absent. The current levels of irradiation of population of western Kazakhstan area are conditioned by two constituents - isotopes of radon in apartments and external a gamma is an irradiation of natural radiation nucleotides. Dose got from the sources of techno genic origin, scorned small (less than 0,5 % from the total dose of current irradiation of population of western Kazakhstan area).

The basic potential radiation danger of objects appearing as a result of underground nuclear explosions and mining holes with the high activity sources of ionizing radiations ragged in the process of geophysical researches consists in the discretional hyphen of radiation nucleotides to aquiferous horizons and in petroleum layers (in case of the unauthorized boring drilling and booty of oil).

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STUDY OF HEPATOPROTECTIVE AND HISTOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA ON THE LIVER OF ALBINO RATS (RATTUS ALBUS)

Қанат Улпан Еркінқызы

АБАЙ АТЫНДАҒЫ ҚАЗАҚ ҰЛТТЫҚ ПЕДАГОГИКАЛЫҚ УНИВЕРСИТЕТІ

Б.ғ.д профессор Тұңғышбаева Зина Байбағысқызы

АБАЙ АТЫНДАҒЫ ҚАЗАҚ ҰЛТТЫҚ ПЕДАГОГИКАЛЫҚ УНИВЕРСИТЕТІ

Аннотация: Бауыр ауруы ежелден халық денсаулығының проблемасы болып келеді. Бұл мәселенің әртүрлі этиологиялық агенттері бар, мысалы, бауырдың зақымдалуына немесе некрозына ықпал ететін гепатотоксиндер мен алкогольизм, бактериялар, паразиттер және вирустар сияқты биологиялық факторлар, метаболикалық аурулар, тіпті парацетамолдың немесе төрт хлорлы көміртегінің препараттарының әсері және т.б. Тиімді және қауіпсіз дәрі-дәрмекпен қамтамасыз ету қажеттілігі трендке айналды, өйткені қазіргі заманғы қолжетімді препараттар жанама әсерлері бар және өзіне тән уыттылық тудырады. Сүт қышқылы бактерияларының көзі ретінде жергілікті белгілі коммерциялық ферменттелген екі өнім пайдаланылды. Изоляттар оң бақылау ретінде силимаринмен бірге альбинос егеуқұйрықтарында (*R. albus*) бауырдың зақымдануына байланысты төрт хлорлы көміртегіге гепатопротекторлық және гистологиялық әсерлері үшін зерттелді. Төрт күн бойы альбинос егеуқұйрықтарды сынау топтарына бір реттік сүт қышқылы бактериялары суспензиясы енгізілді, ал оң бақылау тобына силимариннің бір дозасы енгізілді. Нәтижелер силимаринмен индукцияланған топтағы қан сарысуындағы ALT және AST деңгейлерімен салыстырғанда, LAB индукцияланған топта қан сарысуындағы ALT және AST деңгейінің шамалы ғана жоғарылауын көрсетті. Дисперсияның бір жақты талдауын қолдана отырып, сүт қышқылды бактериялардың төрт хлорлы көміртегіге қарсы Силимариннің гепатопротекторлық әсерлерімен салыстырмалы әсерлері бар екендігі ұсынылды. Бұл нәтиже қалыпты гистологияны көрсететін егеуқұйрық бауыр бөлімдерінің гистологиялық зерттеулерімен толықтырылды.

Кілт сөздер: сүт қышқылы бактериялары; гепатопротекторлық әсерлер; Альбинос егеуқұйрықтары

Keywords: lactic acid bacteria; hepatoprotective effects; Albino rats

Кіріспе

Бауыр ауруларының өршуі гепатиттен басталып, циррозға ұласады және бауыр жеткіліксіздігіне немесе гепатомаға әкеледі. Бірақ созылмалы аурудың өршуінің нақты патологиялық механизмдері әлі де түсініксіз [1]. Сонымен қатар, соңғы деректер әртүрлі агенттердің биологиялық факторлар (мысалы, *Fasciola hepatica*, гепатит А вирусы және *Helicobacter spp.*) және аутоиммундық аурулар (иммундық гепатит және бастапқы билиарлы цирроз) сияқты зақымдануға кейбір препараттар мен олардың метаболиттері (парацетамолдың және туберкулезге қарсы препараттардың жоғары дозалары), улы қосылыстар (көміртек тетрахлориді, тиоацетамид, диметилнитрозамин, D-галактозамин/липополисахарид және терт-бутил гидропероксиді) сияқты әртүрлі химиялық заттардың және шамадан тыс алкоголь тұтыну арқылы ықпал ететінін көрсетті. Бұл созылмалы бауыр ауруы мен циррозды жүрек ауруы, инсульт, кеуде ауруы және қатерлі ісік ауруынан кейінгі өлімнің негізгі себептері ретінде 5-ші орынға шығарады [2].

Дегенмен, қазіргі заманғы медицинаның жетістіктеріне қарамастан, бауыр жұмысын бастайтын, органды толық қорғауды қамтамасыз ететін немесе бауыр жасушаларының регенерациясына көмектесетін толық тиімді дәрілер жоқ. Олар әсіресе созылмалы немесе созылмалы түрде қабылдағанда ықтимал жағымсыз әсерлері бар [3]. Сонымен қатар, кейбір журналдарда синтетикалық препараттардың бауыр ауруын жақсартуға аз үлес қосатынын келтіреді [4]. Демек, пробиотиктер бауыр бұзылыстарын емдеуге бейімделген, бұл агенттер тиімдірек және аз уытты болуы керек. Сүт қышқылы бактериялары маңызды ішек микрофлорасы болып табылады және дәстүрлі түрде ірімшік, шарап кокос жаңғағы және ашытылған балық сияқты ашытылған тағамдар мен сусындарды өндіруде қолданылады [5]. Сонымен қатар, бауыр ауруында ішек флорасының маңыздылығын ескере отырып, сүт қышқылды бактериялар (ол пробиотик болып табылады) бауыр энцефалопатиясын жақсарту және бауыр қатерлі ісігінің қаупін азайту үшін тиімді диеталық тәсілді қамтамасыз ете алады.

Сүт қышқылды бактериялардың көптеген фармакологиялық артықшылықтары, мысалы, ішек микробтық жүйесін сақтау және иммундық функцияны жақсарту туралы айтылғанымен, әлі күнге дейін сүт қышқылы бактерияларының гепатопротекторлық әсерін зерттеу үшін аз жұмыс жасалды [6]. Бұл зерттеу коммерциялық қол жетімді ашытылған тамақ өнімдерінде бөлінген сүт қышқылы бактерияларының гепатопротекторлық және гистологиялық әсерін білуге бағытталған. Бұл сонымен қатар фармацевтикалық салаларға бауыр ауруынан өлім-жітім деңгейінің жоғарылауы туралы шешімді ұсынуға көмектеседі, осылайша олар бауырды одан әрі зақымданудан қорғау үшін жаңа және тиімдірек дәрі жасай алады.

Зерттеу әдістері мен материалдары: Сүт қышқылы бактериялары (LAB) суспензиясын дайындау. 2,5 X 10⁶ бактериялық суспензияны дайындау үшін 4 мл LAB түйіршіктері 16 мл 0,1 М фосфат буферінің ерітіндісімен (рН 7,4) суспензияланды. LAB санау үшін Нойбауэр санау камерасы пайдаланылды. Екі санау камерасының екі ішкі бес шаршысы да саналды. Әрбір ішкі шаршыда 25 кіші шаршы болды. Бактерияларды санағаннан кейін жалпы сан мына формула арқылы шешілді:

LAB жасушаларының саны есептеледі

** сұйылту коэффициенті*

$$LAB \text{ саны} = \frac{\text{ } }{0,2 \text{ мм ()} \times 0,1 \text{ ()}}$$

Жануарлардың бауырына эксперимент жүргізу. Бұл зерттеуде салмағы 150-ден 250 граммға дейін (8-12 апталық) жиырма бес (25) аталық альбинос егеуқұйрықтар (R. albus) пайдаланылды. Олар 7 күндік акклиматизациядан өтті және жеке таза акрил торларында 12 күн бойы 20-26 °С бөлме температурасында және бүкіл эксперимент үшін 12/12 сағат жарық/қараңғылық тұрақты жарық циклдарымен орналастырылды. Альбинос егеуқұйрықтары (R. albus) коммерциялық түйіршіктелген егеуқұйрықтары мен сумен қоректендірілді. Бұл жануарларға Институционалдық жануарларды күту және пайдалану комитеті белгілеген нұсқауларға сәйкес күтім жасалды.

Жиырма бес (25) альбинос егеуқұйрықтар (R. albus) келесі кодпен 5 топқа бөлінді:

1-топ (теріс бақылау) – Сүт қышқылы бактерияларын, силимаринді және төрт хлорлы көміртекті қолданбайды.

2-топ – альбинос егеуқұйрықтар сүт қышқылы бактерияларының оқшауланған штамдарымен ауызша тағайындалған (4 күн, күніне 1 рет)

5-топ (Сынақ) – альбинос егеуқұйрықтар сүт қышқылы бактерияларының оқшауланған штаммдарымен (4 күн, күніне бір рет), төрт хлорлы көміртегі индукциясымен (сүт қышқылды бактерияларды соңғы енгізгеннен кейін бір сағаттан кейін) пероз арқылы енгізілген егеуқұйрықтар.

Әртүрлі агенттерді енгізер алдында альбинос егеуқұйрықтар (*R. albus*) 7 күн бойы акклиматизациядан өтті. Бұл олардың жаңа ортаға бейімделуіне мүмкіндік берді.

Сүт қышқылы бактериялары. 2 және 5 топтағы альбинос егеуқұйрықтарға (*R. albus*) төрт күн бойы оқшауланған сүт қышқылы бактерияларының 1,0 мл 2,5 x 10⁶ суспензиясы (16 мл 0,1 М PBS буферіне 400 мкл) ауызша берілді[7].

Силимарин. 2-топтағы (оң бақылау) альбинос егеуқұйрықтарға (*R. albus*) төрт күн бойы 1,0 мл силимарин суспензиясы (210 мг таза силимарин/16 мл 0,85% NSS) ауызша берілді.

0,85% Қалыпты тұзды ерітінді. Альбинос егеуқұйрықтарға (*R. albus*) 1-топқа (теріс бақылау) және 3-топқа (бақылауға) төрт күн бойы 1 мл 0,85% Қалыпты тұзды ерітінді ішке берілді.

Көміртек төртхлориді. Әртүрлі заттарды түпкілікті енгізгеннен кейін бір сағаттан кейін 20 альбинос егеуқұйрықтарға (*R. albus*) төрт хлорлы көміртек пен зәйтүн майымен (2 мл/кг 50% т/ж) ауызша енгізілді. Енгізілетін доза әр альбинос егеуқұйрықтың (*R. albus*) салмағына байланысты болды.

Қан жинау. Қан үлгілері 18 сағаттан кейін жүрек пункциясы арқылы алынды. Жиналған үлгілер қызыл эвакуацияланған түтіктерге салынып, бөлме температурасында 60 минут ішінде ұюға рұқсат етілді. Сарысуды бөлуге мүмкіндік беру үшін 10 минут бойы 2000 айн/мин центрифугалау жүргізілді. Сарысу үлгілері биохимиялық көрсеткіштерге – аспартатаминотрансфераза және аланинаминотрансферазаға сыналған. Әдістемелердің дұрыс орындалуын қамтамасыз ету үшін келесі процедуралар ғылыми кеңесшінің көмегімен орындалды. Қан алынғаннан кейін альбинос егеуқұйрықтарға (*R. albus*) жатыр мойнының дислокациясы арқылы декапитация жасалынды. Осыдан кейін бауыр тіндері кесілді және бекітуді бастау үшін дереу 10% бейтарап буферлі формалині бар стерильді бұрандалы қақпақ контейнерінде сақталды.

Гепатопротекторлық әсерлерін анықтау. Сүт қышқылы бактерияларының гепатопротекторлық әсерін өлшеу үшін альбинос егеуқұйрықтардың (*R. albus*) сарысу үлгілеріндегі AST және ALT деңгейлері өлшенді. Альбинос егеуқұйрық (*R. albus*) үшін анықтамалық мән ALT 18 – 45 U/L, ал AST үшін анықтамалық мән 7 – 143 U/L [8].

Гистологиялық әсерлерін зерттеу. Бауыр тіндері 10% бейтарап буферлі формалинмен бекітілгеннен кейін өңделді және парафинге салынды. Бөлімдер кесілді және гематоксилинмен және эозинмен боялды. Барлық тіндерді жеңіл микроскоппен қарап, бауыр тіндерінің кез келген өзгерістер архитектурасын талдадық.

Зерттеу нәтижелерін талдау:

Гепатопротекторлық әсерлері. Сарысулық бауыр маркерлерінің, аспартатаминотрансферазаның және аланинаминотрансферазаның белсенділігін қолдану арқылы сүт қышқылы бактериялары штаммдарының гепатопротекторлық әсері өлшенді. Аспартатаминотрансфераза мен аланинаминотрансферазаның жалпы нәтижелері 1-кестеде берілген.

Кесте-1. Аспартатаминотрансфераза мен аланинаминотрансфераның жалпы нәтижелері

ТОП	ALT (анықтама)	Орташа±SD	AST (анықтама)	Орташа±SD
ТЕРІС БАҚЫЛАУ	18-45 U/L	56.4±16.55	74-143 U/L	134.85±2.33
СИЛИМАРИН+CCL4	18-45 U/L	73±4.24	74-143 U/L	145.75±23.55
NSS+CCL4	18-45 U/L	167.82±204.97	74-143 U/L	193.4±42.13
LAB + CCL4	18-45 U/L	46.2±24.04	74-143 U/L	159.70±19.94
ЗЕРТХАНАЛЫҚ СЫНАҚ	18-45 U/L	36.6±36.11	74-143 U/L	126.53±27.17

Бірінші топ (теріс бақылау) әртүрлі егеуқұйрық топтарының қан сарысуындағы ALT және AST деңгейлерінің бастапқы деңгейлері үшін зерттеушілер үшін негіз болды. Сынақ нәтижесінде қан сарысуындағы ALT деңгейі $56,4 \pm 16,55$ анықталды, бұл $134,85 \pm$ -мен шамалы жоғарылауды көрсетті. AST $2,33$ деңгейі қалыпты диапазонға түсті. Бұл жалпы альбинос егеуқұйрықтардың (*R. albus*) бауырының жағдайы жақсы екенін білдіреді. Дегенмен, теріс бақылаумен салыстырғанда $0,85\%$ NSS көміртегі тетрахлоридімен индукцияланған альбинос егеуқұйрықтарының нәтижелерінде елеулі өзгерістер байқалды. Сарысудағы ALT және AST концентрациясының айтарлықтай жоғарылауы альбинос егеуқұйрық бауырларының төрт хлорлы көміртегімен зақымдалғанын көрсетті. Бауыр жасушаларында ALT және AST жоғары концентрациялары бар, бұл гепатоциттер зақымдалғанда, бұл бауырға тән ферменттердің қан сарысуына ағып кетуін тудырады, бұл олардың қалыпты деңгейінің жоғарылауын тудырады. Сондай-ақ олар екі ферменттің жоғарылауын қосады. жасушалардың зақымдануының және бауыр жасушалық мембранасының функционалдық тұтастығын жоғалтуының жақсы көрсеткіштері [9].

Сурет-1. Н&Е бояуын қолдана отырып, егеуқұйрық бауырының гистологиялық талдауы (А-1топ, В-2топ, С-3топ, Д-4 топ,Е-5 топ)

Сарысу маркерінің ALT деңгейінің жоғарылауы силимаринмен және төрт хлорлы көміртегімен өңделген топта да байқалды. Сондай-ақ топтың сарысуындағы AST деңгейінің аздап жоғарылауы байқалды. Бұл силимаринді қолдану уақытының ұзақтығына байланысты болуы мүмкін. Емдеу уақыты силимариннің гепатопротекторлық әсерін көрсетуі үшін тым қысқа болды. Сүт қышқылы бактерияларымен индукцияланған альбинос егеуқұйрықтарының (*R. albus*) топтары (2-топ және 5-топ) сарысудағы ALT және AST деңгейлерін айтарлықтай өзгертті. Силимарин болып табылатын оң бақылауға әкеледі, сүт қышқылы бактерияларымен өңделген топта қан сарысуындағы ALT деңгейінің шамалы ғана жоғарылауы байқалады. Бұл жерде *Lactobacillus plantarum* бауырды қорғау қабілеті AST және ALT деңгейінің төмендігімен анықталды.

Қорытынды.

Lactobacillus plantarum 2-нің альбинос егеуқұйрықтардағы карбонтетрахлоридке (CCL4) индукцияланған бауыр жарақатына гепатопротекторлық әсері оның сарысудағы аспаратаминотрансфераза және аланинаминотрансфераза деңгейлерін төмендетеді және микроскопиялық тұрғыдан қарағанда қалыпты бауыр тінін көрсетті. Нәтижелер оқшауланған сүт қышқылы бактериялары альбинос егеуқұйрықтардың бауырын қорғай алатынын көрсетеді. Сүт қышқылды бактериялардың гепатоциттерді қорғау қабілеті ішке қабылданған LAB ас қорыту жолында бар ас қорыту ферменттерімен әрекеттескенде және олардың компоненттерін ішек арқылы бауырға сіңіргеннен кейін қадағалағаннан басталады, онда олар өздерінің пробиотикалық әсерін көрсетеді. Онда олар сүт қышқылы бактериялары патогендерге және басқа гепатотоксикалық агенттерге қарсы тосқауылдық әсер жасайды және қысқа тізбекті май қышқылдары мен бактериоциндер сияқты реттеуші факторларды түзеді [12]. AST және ALT

деңгейлерінің нәтижелеріне және альбинос егеуқұйрықтардың (*R. albus*) бауыр тінінің гистологиялық зерттеуіне сүйене отырып, сүт қышқылы бактерияларының тиімділігі оң бақылаумен, яғни силимаринмен салыстырмалы болды. Сонымен қатар, силимариннің, коммерциялық гепатопротекторлық агенттің және CCL4 индукцияланған бауыр зақымдануындағы сүт қышқылды бактериялардың сарысу маркерлік ферменттеріне әсерлері арасында айтарлықтай айырмашылық жоқ.

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DEVELOPMENT OF GARDENING IN CONDITIONS OF THE SOUTHEAST KAZAKHSTAN'S FOOTHILL ZONE USING THE TECHNIQUES OF WATER-SAVING INNOVATION TECHNOLOGY

N.Sh. Suleimenova

Professor, Kazakh National Agrarian research University, Kazakhstan

A.Togisbayeva

PhD- doctorate of the "Ecology" department, Kazakh National Agrarian research University, Kazakhstan

Abstract: This article aims to develop gardening in the arid conditions of the foothill zone of southeastern Kazakhstan by using water-saving innovative technologies. The research covered the influence of the water-holding polymer "Aquasorb" on agrophysical properties of soil and physiological water regime indicators of wood and fluid crops (apple tree) in experimental gardens under the typical conditions of the study zone. It was established that the polymer increases the common and productive supply of moisture in the soil and improves agrophysical properties, creates more favorable conditions for the adaptation and development of fruit crops, in particular apple trees. Increases the drought tolerance of plants in terms of heat resistance, moisture adherent abilities, general infection and the content of mobile moisture in tissues from apple leaves.

The presence of the hydrogel in the root layer increases moisture-conductive ability of the apple leaves by 11 %, by 4-8 (18) % increases the content of hydration and mobile moisture in each option compared to control. Under the arid conditions of Southeast Kazakhstan, in the experiment the best indicators of moisture holding and hydration of leaves were established at the dosage of 1.5 kg/m³, in more harsh years the best indicators of apple-tree growing were obtained at applying a rate of 2.0 kg/m³ of the hydrogel in the root layer of soil.

A high degree of water retention and satisfactory tissue hydration were found in *Malus cv*, which indicates their ability to adapt to changing conditions of climate change and water supply of fruit crops, apple trees in particular.

Key words: innovative technology, water-saving methods, hydrogel - "AQUASORB", agrophysical factors, soil, fruit crops, apple tree, adaptation, arid conditions.

Introduction

Research relevance. In the 21st century, growing human population, depletion of plant resources, development of the main areas of productive agricultural land and increase in technogenic pressure on the natural environment have become one of the factors hindering social and economic development for many countries of the world community (Myrzakhanova et al.2014). At the same time, climatic changes in the ecosystem of the biosphere make their negative role. The influence of climatic and socio-economic factors predetermined the shortage of water resources in the entire Central Asian region. In Kazakhstan, this figure is 40% below the world level and is projected to fall another 30% by 2030. In most agricultural zones, the general dynamics of global warming is traced, which contributes to the movement of natural zones in a northerly direction, creating conditions for expanding the cultivar area of promising crops and flora (Mirzadinov et al. 2009), but in parallel leads to the display of desertification and degradation of natural ecosystems [1, 2].

Climate fluctuations in the direction of warming, as a rule, lead to a shortage of water resources (Nazarova, 2014). Therefore, climate aridization and water shortage are becoming

the leading ecological and biological problem of plant introduction, especially on the territory of agricultural zones in the conditions of growing agricultural and fruit crops [3].

Increasing the potential and effective management of soil water properties is possible using various water-saving technologies (Gundyryn et al, 2014 and Genkel, 1982), one of which is the use of water-retaining polymers or hydrogels in arid and semi-arid areas to grow plants and increase their productivity [4, 5].

The deficit is caused by the lack of atmospheric moisture and its inefficient conservation (gravitational runoff of water from the root layer and loss of moisture during evaporation). One of the conditions for increasing the range of cultigenous plants is to reduce the physical evaporation of soil moisture for more complete accumulation and use against the background of an unstable pattern of precipitation throughout the entire annual cycle. Therefore, the development of consumer gardening in arid conditions of the Republic's territories using water-saving methods of innovative technology is an urgent strategic task of agricultural science.

In this connection, the research purpose in this article was to determine the effectiveness of subsoil irrigation' effect with three norms of the AQUASORB polymer hydrogel on soil's agrophysical properties and the water regime of tree and fruit species when growing in arid conditions of Kazakhstan [6].

Materials and Research Methods

The test site of research is the arid zone of irrigated agriculture, characterized by sharply continental climate, low humidity, lots of sunshine, a short, but quite cold winter.

The formation of climate features and soil in the region is subject to the law of vertical zoning, which is most clearly expressed in the central part of the Northern Tien Shan, formed by the Zailiyskiy Alatau ridge (Recommendations, 2005). Experimental studies were carried out at the territory of the research and experimental station of KazNAIU "Agrouniversitet", 37 km and the private farm "Turgen", 59 km from Almaty, which are located in the Enbekshikazakh district of the Almaty region [7].

The regions are characterized by hot summers with frequent atmospheric and soil droughts, cold winters with little snow cover and soils with a humus content of 3 to 4%. The annual temperature amplitude reaches a maximum, which determines the sharply continental climate at the observation points. By the middle of summer, the average daily air temperature in the regions reaches +22+24°C, with an absolute maximum of up to +38 C° and humidity of 37–45%. January temperature is in the range of -10-20 °C with an absolute minimum of -43 °C. The snow cover reaches 25-30 cm, the amount of precipitation is within 350 mm in the Enbekshikazakhsky region.

Objects of study: water-saving innovative technologies (hydrogel, drip irrigation), the tested fruit crop, an apple tree in arid conditions of South-East Kazakhstan in a private agro-industrial company (PAC).

Research methods: classical generally accepted in plant growing, introduction, plant physiology, as well as the main methods of empirical research (observation, comparison, measurement and experiment), which allows us to give a comparative assessment of the adaptive capabilities of experimental apple plants using various water-saving technologies. Installation and conducting of agrotechnical experiments were made by the method of trial plots according to B. A. Dospikhov. [8,9]. Experimental plots with an area of 1 ha were created with experiments in five variants on using two innovative agricultural technologies - hydrogel, drip irrigation in comparison with furrow irrigation. 2 experimental variants of 0.25 hectares divided into drip irrigation and control. The remaining area of 0.5 ha was used for the experiment with the water-absorbing polymer "AQUASORB" with three norms - 1.0 kg/m³, 1.5 kg/m³, 2.0 kg/m³.

Novelty of research. For the first time in Kazakhstan, various concentrations of moisture-swelling polymer hydrogels and drip irrigation are being tested during creation of industrial and innovative orchards of fruit crops (apple trees).

Results and discussion

The main factor determining the life process of the species in an arid climate is the ability of plants to endure high summer temperatures in conditions of lack of soil and atmospheric moisture. During atmospheric drought, leaf transpiration increases so much that the loss of water cannot be replaced by roots, even if there is sufficient water in the soil, causing disturbances in metabolism and cellular structures (Genkel, 1982). One of the indicators of drought resistance is heat tolerance of plants in determining the impact of high temperatures on maintaining the stability of physiological processes in plant leaf tissues [5].

Experimental plants showed differences in their ability to tolerate high summer temperatures, under conditions of lack of soil and atmospheric moisture. The first signs of damage to the leaf blades of an apple tree are considered when up to 15% of the area on the leaf blades are damaged by spots. The level of heat resistance of individual species goes from medium to low scores, dropping to 15-35%.

The presence of hydrogel in the root zone increases the heat resistance of the apple tree and allows them to better adapt to the adverse temperature effects of the external environment. Among the three options for introducing the hydrogel "AQUASORB" into the soil on the experimental fields, the indicators of heat resistance increase at an application rate of the hydrogel of 1.0 kg/m³ up to 10-25%. With an increase in the water-retaining polymer in the root layer of the soil up to 2.0 kg/m³, the heat resistance increased up to 15–35%.

The water regime of plants determines resistance of vital processes to the influence of external environment in order to maintain stability of all physiological processes taking place in body tissues. It is directly related to leaf physiology, its ability to accumulate and retain moisture for a long time, and also reflects soil moisture conditions that affect the rate of transpiration (Genkel, 1982).

As the results of studies have shown, drought resistance among experimental plants varies widely, depending on generic, species, varietal characteristics, age and climatic conditions of the growing season. High water-retaining capacity (45-60%) was noted in tree species in all experiments at the beginning of the summer period on experimental and control plots.

It has been established that the polymer increases the total and productive supply of moisture in soil and improves agrophysical properties, creates more favorable conditions for adaptation and development of fruit crops, in particular apple trees. Also it increases the drought resistance of plants in terms of heat resistance, water-holding capacity, total water content and mobile moisture content in tissues from apple leaves.

The presence of hydrogel in the root layer increases the water-holding capacity of apple leaves by 11%, i.e. by 4-8% increases the content of hydration and mobile moisture in each studied variant compared to the control. Experimentally revealed four levels of heat resistance in experimental plants: - high degree (0-15%); - increased degree (16-50%); - medium degree (51-80%); - low degree (more than 81-100%).

In the experimental arid conditions of South-East Kazakhstan, the best indicators of moisture retention and hydration of leaves were established at an application rate of 1.5 kg / m³, in more severe years, growing apple trees, the best indicators were obtained at a rate of 2.0 kg / m³ of hydrogel in the root soil layer .

A high degree of water retention and satisfactory tissue hydration were found in the apple tree (*Malus cv*), indicating their ability to adapt to changing climatic conditions and the water supply of fruit crops, in particular the apple tree.

By the beginning of autumn, there is a decrease in average daily temperatures and an increase in humidity. By the end of the growing season, the leaves are aging, which is associated with the weakening of plant life processes. For all species of plants in the options with the hydrogel, an increase in the content of mobile moisture in the leaves with 11-26% and total hydration by 2-9% with a total decrease in water retention to 7-21 (39%) was observed. Water holding polymer in the root zone evens out by 3-14% indicators of the water regime of plants in all versions.

According to the results of the studies, it was found that in all 3 variants of the experiment, the polymer has a beneficial effect on soil structure, improving its water-air and agrophysical properties.

In the control section of the studied Enbekshikazaksky district, the density of the upper soil horizon of 10-20 cm is 1.3 g/cm^3 , 30-40 cm- $1.4-1.6 \text{ g/cm}^3$, which corresponds to the critical density of the water-air regime's agrophysical indicators necessary for the development of root plant systems. When the hydrogel is applied at the rate of 1 kg/m^3 , 1.5 kg/m^3 , 2.0 kg/m^3 , the soil density in the soil horizon of 30-40 cm (root layer) is reduced to $1.2-1.3 \text{ g/cm}^3$.

It was established that the hydrogel in the root zone provides an increase in moisture content and increases the supply of productive moisture in soil. It was established that in July, in the hottest and most dry vegetation period, moisture content in soil at a depth of 30-40 cm in the first version is higher than 1.3 times, in the second option -1.7 times, in the third version - 2 times compared to the typical harrow method. Whereas, the soil moisture index increases from 27 to 50% in July in hydrogel options compared to control. The largest increase in soil moisture was found when the hydrogel was introduced at a concentration of 2.0 kg/m^3 . On average, when using a hydrogel with a norm of introduction of 1.0 kg/m^3 , 1.5 kg/m^3 , 2.0 kg/m^3 in July, moisture reserves at the soil depth 30-40 cm amounted to $340.0-470.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$ in , in control $160.0-360.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$.

The resulting experimental materials made possible to draw up a recommendation for production, where farmers use rational water -saving techniques for innovative technology while growing apple trees in conditions of the Enbekshikazakhsy district obtaining a high harvest of fruits with the optimal environmental agroecosystem of the fruit crops and high economic efficiency.

Conclusion

Applying the water-retaining polymer "AQUASORB" under the tree-fruit crop of apple trees in arid arid foothill conditions of southeastern Kazakhstan, increases the total and productive supply of moisture, improves aeration and agrophysical properties of soil in root zone of plants, creates more favorable conditions for adaptation and development of plants by increasing the heat and drought resistance of tree crops.

The presence of hydrogel in the root layer increases water-retaining capacity of leaves by 11%, increases water content and mobile moisture by 4-8% in each variant compared to the control. The best indicators of water-retaining capacity and water content of the leaves of apple trees were established at a rate of 1.5 kg/m^3 , in more severe years, growing apple trees, the best indicators were obtained at a rate of 2.0 kg/m^3 of hydrogel in the root layer. A high degree of water retention and satisfactory tissue hydration were found in *Malus cv* apple trees, indicating their ability to adapt to changing conditions of climate change and water supply to fruit crops, in particular apple trees.

By the beginning of autumn, there is a decrease in average daily temperatures and an increase in humidity. By the end of the growing season, the leaves age, which is associated with a weakening of the vital processes of plants. All plant species in the variants with hydrogel are

characterized by an increase in the content of mobile moisture in leaves from 11% to 26% in dry years, 53% and total water content also by 2–9%, with a general decrease in water-retaining capacity to 7%–21%. The water-retaining polymer in the root zone evens out the indicators of the water regime of plants when growing fruit crops.

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